

Stability Constants of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Dioxouranium(II) and Thorium(IV) with Complexones and Isomeric Alanines

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The stability sequence of the complexes of U^{IV} and Th^{IV} has been reported^{1,2} to be $U^{IV} > Th^{IV}$, which is justified on the basis of their charge-size relationship. In UO_2^{II} ion the $O=U=O$ moiety is linear³; this linearity is likely to cause some steric hindrance during hetero-chelation, and the charge-size ratio may also be less favourable as compared to U^{IV} . The present work is intended to report the stability sequence between UO_2^{II} and Th^{IV} ions for their mixed ligand complexes with the two isomeric alanines, α -alanine (α -ala) and β -alanine (β -ala) containing a complexone as primary ligand. The complexones used are iminodiacetate (IMDA), nitrilotriacetate (NTA), 2-hydroxyethylethylenediaminetriacetate (HEDTA), ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA), 1,2-diaminocyclohexanetetraacetate (CDTA) and diethylenetriaminepentaacetate (DTPA).

Results and Discussion

The observed stability sequence for the mixed ligand complexes with respect to the primary ligands has been found to be $IMDA > NTA > HEDTA > EDTA > CDTA > DTPA$, which is opposite of the known sequence for the corresponding MA chelates^{4,5}. The factors responsible for the observed sequence may be the electrostatic effect involved in the combination of L with MA (the MAL complexes are formed in two steps as $M + A \rightleftharpoons MA$, $MA + L \rightleftharpoons MAL$ in the present work as indicated by the titration curves) and also the statistical effect. The $\Delta \log K$ ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$) values are all negative due to

TABLE I—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF THE BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES				
$I=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{KNO}_3), \text{Temp.}=25^\circ$				
Metal ion	Formation constant	α -ala	β -ala	
UO_2^{II}	$\log K_{ML}^M$	7.79	7.70	
	$\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$	7.39	7.09	
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (IMDA)	7.36	7.35	
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (NTA)	7.34	7.21	
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (HEDTA)	6.94	6.85	
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (EDTA)	6.74	6.73	
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (CDTA)	6.70	6.35	
	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (DTPA)	5.84	5.80	
	Th^{IV}	$\log K_{ML}^M$	8.51	8.37
		$\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$	8.40	9.29
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (IMDA)		8.47	8.36	
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (NTA)		8.37	8.34	
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (HEDTA)		8.27	8.25	
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (EDTA)		7.23	6.79	
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (CDTA)		6.81	6.64	
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (DTPA)		5.89	5.88	
Standard deviation = ± 0.01 to 0.05 .				

NOTES

the charged nature of the primary and secondary ligands. Similar trends have been reported for such mixed ligand complexes with the 3d-metal ions⁶ and the lanthanides⁷.

The stability sequence with respect to the two metal ions has been found to be $UO_2^{II} < Th^{IV}$ for the mixed ligand MAL complexes and the binary ML and ML_2 complexes. Thus, the sequence $U^{IV} > Th^{IV}$ is found to be reversed on going from U^{IV} to UO_2^{II} . The observed stability order may be a consequence of (i) greater positive charge on Th^{IV} and hence more favourable entropy factor (ΔS) and charge neutralisation effect associated with the formation of its MAL complexes, (ii) steric hindrance caused by the linearity of O=U=O moiety and (iii) possibly greater ionic potential of Th^{IV} than that of UO_2^{II} .

The observed stability sequence, α -ala $>$ β -ala in both binary and ternary systems agrees well with the general trend^{6,8}, 5-membered chelate ring $>$ 6-membered chelate ring. β -Alanine is, however, more basic than α -alanine. This may perhaps be responsible for the closeness in the values of the formation constants with the two isomeric amino acids.

Experimental

Uranyl and thorium nitrates were of AnalaR grade and other chemicals of G.R. (E. Merck) or A.R. (Fluka) grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The final concentrations of metal

ion (M) and primary ligand (A) were kept at $[M] = [A] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, whereas the secondary ligand (L) was taken in a five-fold excess. The formation constants $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (the symbols have their usual meanings) were determined as reported earlier⁹. The refined values of formation constants are reported in Table 1.

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